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INTERSECTIONALITY BETWEEN GENDER, RACE AND CLASS IN THE (RE)PRODUCTION OF SOCIAL (DIS)EQUALITY.

Luzia Costa Becker

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Policy Statement

Gender inequality continues to permeate all areas of society, posing a significant challenge to the consolidation of democracy in the global context. The critique offered by feminist thought has enriched social studies by highlighting how the gender category reveals the hierarchies present in the social world. However, through an intersectional approach, new evidence has emerged by linking gender with other categories, such as class and race, enhancing the ability to analyze the complexities of social phenomena. With this understanding of the issue, how can we implement greater efficiency in designing and executing policies aimed at eradicating inequalities between men and women, as well as addressing and preventing violence against women? In the context of the 2030 Agenda, specifically SDG 5 – Gender Equality; SDG 10 – Reducing Inequalities; and more recently, SDG 18 – Racial Equality, proposed by Brazil due to the urgent need to confront structural racism, governmental Women's Policy Organizations (WPOs) are deemed essential for addressing the nuances of gender inequality in the formulation of public policies aimed at overcoming social disparities.

Background

Historically, a role of submission has been imposed on women within the social hierarchy based on moral and ethical principles that have shaped patriarchal Western culture. This culture can be traced back to the Greek^[1] world, where man is considered the being of reason (an attribute of the soul). At the same time, the woman—the enslaved person, the elderly, the child, and all that signifies fragility—represents the being of emotion (an attribute of the body). Consequently, the former dominates the latter due to the perceived superiority of reason over emotion. This hierarchical perspective has influenced various fields of knowledge. It suggests, in the modern world, that men hold a superior position on the social ladder, as whose economic and productive activities prevail. (1994). This characterization, which broadly defines men as aggressive, leading, rational, assertive, and intellectual, and women as passive, obedient, emotional, weak, and physical, although it clarifies the existing social hierarchies, is nevertheless insufficient to understand the complexity and multiple forms of social inequality and subordination.

In this way, theoretical reflection and practical reality have shown that gender, class, and race must be interconnected within social complexity. These axes of oppression and subjection reflect the macroscopic reality of systems such as patriarchy, capitalism, and racism alongside the microcosmic reality formed by the embodiment of social relations between individuals.

Male supremacy structures inequalities in relations between men and women, which disadvantage the latter. However, these inequalities take on particular configurations when present in the frameworks of class and race. The ideological and material forms of oppression experienced by white women from privileged classes do not face the same experiences as black women from lower classes. The colonial impacts of slavery, with the accompanying racist ideology, along with the devastating effects of the capitalist “machine,” have contributed to significant social exclusion. This has led to the over-representation of the black population in poverty in both the US and Brazil, particularly among women (Davis: 2016).

Using intersectionality[2], we consider the three intersecting forms of oppression and subjectivation that shape the experiences of black women from working-class backgrounds. To overcome the social asymmetries arising from the intersection and reciprocal constitution of these three categories in contemporary societies, the 2030 agenda for global transformation involving SDGs 5, 10, and 18, as well as the Governmental Organizations for Women's Policies (OPMs), especially the municipal administrative departments, is indicated to address social inequalities related to gender.

Findings

The 2030 Agenda serves as a guide for the international community and an action plan to place the world on a more sustainable and resilient path by 2030 (UN: 2015). It proposes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and 169 targets to eradicate poverty and promote a decent quality of life for all within the planet's limits. As comprehensive, cross-cutting commitments, when fulfilled, they have the potential to profoundly and positively transform society.

In the case of SDG 10, as well as seeking to promote the social, economic, and political inclusion of all, the goal is to ensure equal opportunities and reduce inequalities, mainly by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies, and practices and promoting

appropriate legislation, policies, and actions in this regard. However, despite having made some progress in recent years, according to the International Labor Organization (ILO), the wealthiest 10 percent of the world's population is responsible for more than 50 percent of global income. In comparison, the poorest half only receives 6.5 percent of that income (UN: 2019). In this unequal distribution, geographical location plays a significant role: extreme poverty is concentrated in the least developed countries, areas affected by armed conflicts, and remote rural areas. Inequality is more pronounced in Southern Africa and Latin America and is increasing within individual countries, disproportionately affecting vulnerable groups, including women (UN Women, 2024). According to the Global Sustainable Development Report 2023, one in six people worldwide has experienced some form of discrimination, with women being disproportionately affected.

Although research shows that more egalitarian laws are associated with more women working, higher salaries, more women-owned businesses, and more women in management positions and parliaments (World Bank 2023), implying a more significant collective benefit, the systematic unequal legal treatment of women constitutes a substantial impediment to their economic participation, including for female entrepreneurs and those aspiring to start a business. Therefore, solid and comprehensive legal frameworks are needed to tackle this impediment that aims for gender equality and the fulfillment of women's rights in practice (World Bank Group: 2024). Inequality puts at risk the little progress that has been made in recent decades in terms of gender equality and women's rights, who still suffer from significant economic, legal, political, and social disparities. The World Bank estimates that approximately 2.4 billion women worldwide do not have the same financial rights as men (UN: 2022).

Regarding SDG 5, the Global Gender Inequality Report (Global Gender Gap Report 2024) shows that the overall gender gap in 2024 for all 146 participating countries – measured across four areas: economic participation and opportunities, education, health, and political empowerment – has decreased by 0.1% (from 68.5% to 68.6%) compared to 2023. However, the expectation for achieving parity remains 134 years from now, about five generations beyond the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target of 2030.

The 2024 Global Gender Gap Index shows that although no country has achieved full gender parity, 97% of the economies included in this edition have closed more than 60% of their gaps, an improvement from 85% in 2006.

European economies occupy seven of the top 10 positions globally. In addition to Iceland (93.5%), which remains in first place and the only economy that has eliminated more than 90% of its gender gap, Finland (2nd, 87.5%), Norway (3rd, 87.5%), Sweden (5th, 81.6%), Germany (7th, 81%), Ireland (9th, 80.2%), and Spain (10th, 79.7%) stand out. The remaining three positions are held by economies from East Asia and the Pacific (New Zealand, 4th, 83.5%), Latin America and the Caribbean (Nicaragua, 6th, 81.1%), and Sub-Saharan Africa (Namibia, 8th, 80.5%). Lithuania (11th, 79.3%) and Belgium (12th, 79.3%) fell out of the top 10, with Spain and Ireland moving up 8 and 2, respectively, to join the top performers in 2024. Among the 146 economies included in the 2024 index, the Health and Survival gender gap was reduced by 96%, the Educational Attainment gap by 94.9%, the Economic Participation and Opportunity gap by 60.5%, and the Political Empowerment gap by 22.5% (Global Gender Gap Report 2024).

Brazil fell to 70th in the 2024 index, closing 71.6% of the gender gap. This represents a reduction of 1 percentage point (from 72.6% in 2023) and a drop of 13 positions compared to last year's ranking. Economic equality fell slightly compared to 2023, at 66.7% compared to 67.0%. However, the country maintained parity in the labor market and achieved its highest score in senior leadership positions (66.1%). Female participation in the workforce increased by 0.7 percentage points compared to 2023, reaching 72.6%. Despite this, it is still 4.5 points below the country's best result (77.2% in 2021).

At the educational level, Brazil achieved effective parity at 99.6%. There was no change in the health and survival sub-index, which remains at 98%. In politics, the country aligns with the global average, scoring 22%, a decrease from 26.3% in 2023. This decline is primarily attributed to the reduced representation of women at the ministerial level (Forbes Woman: 2024). This decrease is linked to stereotypes that disconnect the image of women from politics and the lack of support in these spaces. The political arena is hostile to women, fostering violence rooted in gender and ethnic-racial prejudices. Therefore, increasing the number of female political leaders, mainly black and working-class women, necessitates prioritizing public policies addressing social vulnerability and bolstering rights.

In this context, the Brazilian government aims to reduce disparities between men and women of different racial and ethnic backgrounds through the Ministry of Racial Equality. On November 15, 2024, during the G20 Social, the country voluntarily launched SDG 18—Racial Equality.

Among the goals are eliminating all forms of violence, in addition to racism and discrimination, guaranteeing access to justice and fair representation, promoting full reparation for socio-economic and cultural violations, territorial losses, and environmental impacts on their territories, ensuring adequate housing, access to quality health care, quality education and respect for linguistic diversity. From the perspective of the 2030 Agenda, the federal government has encouraged mayors to integrate the 17 SDGs into their Multi-Year Plan (PPA) to participate in federal and state policies, programs, and projects that will contribute to the sustainable development of their municipality.

Considering the intersectionality of gender, to access these resources, it is of fundamental importance for the municipality to have bodies that manage public policies to guarantee rights, promote equality, and incorporate women as political subjects. The institutionalization[4] and strengthening of Governmental Bodies for Women's Policies (OPM), understood as tools for the formulation and implementation of public policies for women, is essential in the state, district, and municipal administrative structure as a way of bringing the actions of public authorities to women's daily lives.

The existence of an OPM within administrative structures increases the likelihood of better coordination among the entities that support women in their diverse and multifaceted needs. These entities typically improve indicators related to women's issues and contribute to overall progress. According to data from the Secretariat for Institutional Articulation and Thematic Actions (SAIAT) under the Secretariat for Women's Policies (SPM-PR), 61% of OPMs established in various municipalities are designated as coordinators (associated with mayors' offices or other secretariats), 27% are secretaries or sub-secretaries, and 12% have different titles, such as directors, managers, centers, and superintendencies (National Forum of OPMs: 2014, p. 16). Notably, establishing a municipal secretariat facilitates the execution of local actions to ensure women's rights, thus enabling improved coordination of efforts focused on gender equality and social well-being (Forum Nacional de OPMs: 2014). Furthermore, its institution must consider the social, ethnic, racial, and political demands of women in a wide variety of areas, such as Education, Work, Health, Combating Violence, Political Participation, Public Security, and Economic Development, always respecting the diversity of women.

Of Brazil's 5,565 municipalities, less than 700 have secretariats dedicated exclusively to women (Maciel: 2024). As a result, implementing projects drawn up at the federal level, specifically by the Ministry of Women's Affairs, is hampered because the funds must be passed on to the women's secretariat in the municipality. The Ministry of Women's Affairs aims to have 2,000 municipal secretariats for women by December 2026, just over 35% of whom are women (Maciel: 2024).

Recommendations

- Create and strengthen OPMs to formulate and implement public policies for women in the state, district, and municipal administrative structures. This will ensure that public authorities' actions reach women daily. Specifically, secretariats for women's policies at the municipal level will be created to improve the implementation of local actions to guarantee women's rights, thus enabling better coordination of efforts to achieve gender equality and social well-being.
- Increasing the number of women in public administration involves boosting women's participation in public departments and activities, fostering equal debate among all genders, and avoiding the preferential appointment of men to commission positions. In other words, gender equality should serve as a qualitative criterion when selecting service providers and suppliers for the... administration.
- Increase the federal budget for “evidence-based, equality-promoting public policies to prevent and end violence against women and girls, in all its diversity,” enforcing “the Maria da Penha Law in all cases of domestic violence – paternal, fraternal, lesbian relationships, and in domestic work, also ensuring its application to violence against trans women,” as well as ‘resuming the evaluation and replanning of the National Plan to Combat Sexual Abuse and Exploitation conducted by civil society/National Council for the Rights of Children and Adolescents since 2020’ (Luz Report 2023 apud IPEA: 2024).
- Increase investments in women's human capital by prioritizing income transfers that assist families in purchasing essential goods where the social protection network is underdeveloped.

- Provide access to affordable, quality childcare to support women working outside the home or starting their businesses. This will enable more women to enter the workforce and directly generate employment.
- Enhance the representation of women in leadership roles, promoting their involvement in financial institutions and the development of economic policies.
- Eliminate all forms of gender-based ethnic-racial discrimination, ensuring equal opportunities for everyone, regardless of their ethnic or racial background.

Final Considerations

The intersectional perspective not only enhances analytical complexity and depth by addressing various forms of inequality and social subordination, but it also significantly improves the analysis, formulation, and implementation of public policies aimed at combating social inequalities, with a focus on results. In this context, in addition to the need to collectively address domination to avoid perpetuating its reproduction (Hidrata: 2014), it is argued that the presence of OPMs in administrative structures, particularly in municipal secretariats, increases the likelihood of collaboration among agencies that support women in their diversity and varied needs. These agencies are better positioned to improve indicators related to women and contribute to advancements for society as a whole.

References

BANDEIRA, Lourdes Maria; Almeida, Tânia Mara Campos de. A transversalidade de gênero nas Políticas Públicas. Revista do Ceam, v. 2, n. 1, jan./jun. 2013.

CURIEL, Ochy. 2019. Construindo metodologias feministas desde o feminismo decolonial, 2019. In Descolonizar o feminismo, organizado por Paula Balduino de Melo, 32-51. Brasília: Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia de Brasília.

DAVIS, Angela. Mulheres, raça e classe. Candiani, Heci Regina. São Paulo: Boitempo, 2016.

Forum Nacional de Organismos Governamentais de Políticas para as Mulheres – Forum Nacional de OPMs. Guia para criação e implementação de OPM. Brasília. Dezembro de 2014.

Forbes Mulher. Brasil despenca em ranking de igualdade de gênero e ocupa 70º lugar. 12/jun/2024. Disponível em <https://forbes.com.br/forbes-mulher/2024/06/estamos-a-134-anos-da-igualdade-de-genero-segundo-forum-economico-mundial/>. Acesso em 18/fev/2025.

Global Gender Gap Report 2024. Insight Report. Junho, 2024. Disponível em https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2024.pdf. Acesso em 16/fev/2025.

Global Sustainable Development. Report 2023. Key Messages. Disponível em https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2023-09/GSDR%202023%20Key%20Messages_1.pdf. Acesso em 16/fev/2025.

HIRATA, Helena. Gênero, classe e raça Interseccionalidade e consubstancialidade das relações sociais. In Dossiê – Trabalho e Gênero: Controvérsias. Tempo Social, revista de sociologia da USP, v. 26, n. 1, 2014.

IPEA. Agenda 2030: objetivos de desenvolvimento sustentável: avaliação do progresso das principais metas globais para o Brasil: ODS 5: alcançar a igualdade de gênero e empoderar todas as mulheres e meninas. Brasília: 2024. Disponível em https://repositorio.ipea.gov.br/bitstream/11058/14123/1/Agenda_2030_ODS_5_Alcançar_a_igualdade_de_genero.pdf. Acesso em 19/fev/2025.

MACIEL, Alice. País tem menos de 700 secretarias para mulheres, diz ministra sobre desafio da pasta. Agência Pública. 03 de agosto de 2024. Disponível em <https://iclnoticias.com.br/pais-menos-700-secretarias-mulheres-ministra/>. Acesso em 17/fev/2025.

ONU. OIT mostra que apenas 10% dos trabalhadores recebem quase metade do salário global. 4 de julho 2019. Disponível em <https://news.un.org/pt/story/2019/07/1679002>. Acesso em 16/fev/2025.

ONU. Agenda 2030 para o Desenvolvimento Sustentável. Nova York, setembro, 2015. Disponível em <https://brasil.un.org/pt-br/91863-agenda-2030-para-o-desenvolvimento-sustent%C3%A1vel>. Acesso em 17/fev/2025.

UN Women and the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The gender snapshot 2024.

SAFFIOTI, Heleith; ALMEIDA, Suely Souza de. Violência de gênero – Poder e Impotência. Rio de Janeiro: Revinter, 1995.

WORLD BANK GROUP. Women, business and the Law 2024. Disponível em <https://wbl.worldbank.org/en/wbl>. Acesso em 17/fev/2025.

VAITSMAN, Jeni. Hierarquia de Gênero e Iniquidade em Saúde. PHYSIS. Revista de Saúde Coletiva Vol. 4, Número 1, 1994.

[1] For a better understanding of this issue, please take a look at Taylor, Charles. Sources of the Self: The Making of the Modern Identity. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1989.

[2] A perspective that addresses how the intersection of categories and/or systems of oppression of gender, class, race, ethnicity, sexuality, among others, produce inequalities and are mutually constituted. Silva, Roseane Amorim da, & Menezes, Jaileila de Araújo. A interseccionalidade na produção científica brasileira. Pesquisas e Práticas Psicossociais, São João del-Rei, outubro-dezembro de 2020.

[3] The index measures scores on a scale from 0 to 100, which can be interpreted as the distance traveled towards parity (i.e., the percentage of the gender gap that has been closed).

[4] Institutionalization of public policies occurs when public authorities incorporate social demands as actions that produce concrete results in women's lives.

Luzia Costa Becker (InterAgency Institute): PhD in Political Science at IUPERJ (IESP). Postdoctoral fellow at HU Berlin, Germany (2015) and at UFF Niteroi, Brazil (2017).

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3501-2197>

InterAgency Institute

<https://interagency.institute/>
contact@interagency.institute

Review: Danielle Ayres Pinto
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